

Modul4r

Industrial Manufacturing Strategies

For distributed control and resilient, rapidly responsive and reconfigurable supply chains.

Resilience against changes in customer and societal demands and disruptions in the supply chain.

Modular Technologies for flexible manufacturing operations.

Simulation and interfaces to the Industrial Metaverse.

Human centred technologies and upskilling.

